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Sources: Khacikjan, Margarete: The Elamite Language

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Phonology

- /i/ as well as /e/ was contracted before –a: -ni-a>-na, -me-a>-ma
- final /e/ and /i/ were probably neutralized which may be concluded from the alternation –me//–mi, the spelling ‘hube’ alongside ‘hupibe, hupimer’
- Stress:
 - o Not clear
 - o The fact that final /i/ was neutralized (reduced) proves that the final syllable was not stressed
 - o From the fact that the vowel of the second syllable in disyllabic words, expanded by suffixation, was not stressed, it may be assumed that the first syllable was stressed
- Syllable:
 - o (C¹)V(C²); ex.: mu.run
 - o (C¹)VC²C³ - which are the result of certain phonetical process were also common
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Morphology and Syntax

- agglutinative morphology
 - o suffixes joined either to root or stem
 - o root morpheme consists mostly of two C and one or two vowels
 - o stem consisted of a root ending in a C with thematic vowel –i, –u, –a
- nominal structure:
 - o noun consisted of:
 - a root ending in a vowel or consonant; ex.: nap, zana
 - an enlarged root; ex.: kukki
 - a stem followed by class markers; ex.: sunki-r
 - a stem followed by derivational suffixes; ex.: sunki-me
 - a compound stem followed by derivational suffixes; ex.: si-me-n
 - o compound:
 - juxtaposition of two nouns; ex.: kik + murun ‘universe’ (lit.: sky + earth)
 - from the noun and its attribute; ex.: nan + han – te ‘advice’ (word of love)
- verbal structure:
 - o categories: number, person, aspect (expressed by suffixes); tense, mood, voice (expressed by either suffixes and particles?)
 - o stem consisted of a root ending in a vowel or an enlarged stem with athematic

- vowel; ex.: kuk- > kuk-i ‘to protect’
- reduplication of verbal stem:
 - first component usually underwent some modification losing its second C; ex.: tallu- > *tal + tallu- > tatallu- ‘to write’; hapu- > *hap + hapu- > hah(a)pu- ‘to hear’ whole root reduplicated
- numerous compound verbs:
 - ex.: kuk + ta- ‘to defend’ (lit.: defense + put)
 - N + V juxtaposition
- Stem followed by several suffixes
- Final position in suffix chain in both the verbal and nominal conjugation was occupied by the particle –a (relative / connective particle)
- Imperative of the intransitive verb mite/a- ‘to go’ : pure base
- Prepositions and postpositions:
 - No pre- or postpositions proper, but spatial words originating from nouns, verbs, participles
 - Postpositional constructions:
 - Expressing spatial relationship
 - Subordinate word could be a substantive, personal pronoun
 - Enclitic particles from postpositions were also known in older stages – these particles actually functioning as case endings
 - Ex.: -mar ‘from, out of’, -ikki ‘to, towards, into’
 - Compounds: -ikki-mar ‘from, by’ (with animates)
 - Prepositional construction was a word combination of a noun or pronoun in attributive link with the logical subject of the sentence
 - Construction became much simpler in younger states
 - Attributive link of the spatial word with the subject gave place to simple parataxis
- Auxiliary verb: -tarma
 - Usually stands in the same form as the main verb and joins it by means of the element –a: V-a tarma- completeness of an action, intensive, resultative
 - In transitive constructions: V-tam, -bav ‘to be’
 - Ex.: sap murun mazzika tarmac ‘when the earth is completely removed’
- Anomalous verb:
 - Different meaning depending of choice of conjugation (three different ones exist)
 - Use of different conjugation has distinctive function
 - Ex.: pari- first conjugation ‘to come, to reach’, second conjugation ‘to go, to start, to set out’
- Adverbs: forms
 - Pure base
 - Base + classifiers coupled with –a, -na, -da,
 - Reduced forms, lost classifying element
 - Affixes, derivations from participles
 - Compound forms often unanalyzable
- Particles: Attested are:
 - in- negative particle – only used coupled with the class marker of the subject
 - ani, anu – prohibitive particle – was used with conjugation III verbs
 - –ni, -LI, -na precative optative particles
 - –ni, -ut assertive, emphasizing particles
 - –a different functions: adjectival formant (often alternated with the class marker or coupled with them), nominalizing / subordinating element (often coupled with the class marker of the antecedent), connective particle
 - –ta/i different opinions: used in secondary clauses in verbs with pluperfect meaning, in some cases other particles used instead, used with the verb of the secondary clause coupled with nominalizing particles, special usages in

different stages

- -da / -te - not clear